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- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
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SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE EMERGENCE AND FORMATION OF DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: *In this article, an attempt was made to reveal the leading criteria, such as the description of the manifestations of deviant behavior, the negative consequences of deviant behavior, and the manifestations of social norms.*

Key words: *Destructive behavior, deviant behavior, delinquent behavior, eros, thanatos, chromosome theory, endocrine theory, biological theory, destructive institution.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ И ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ДЕСТРУКТИВНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье предпринята попытка выявить ведущие критерии, такие как описание проявлений девиантного поведения, негативные последствия девиантного поведения и проявления социальных норм.*

Ключевые слова: *Деструктивное поведение, девиантное поведение, делинквентное поведение, эрос, танатос, хромосомная теория, эндокринная теория, биологическая теория, деструктивный институт.*

The nature of destructive behavior in humans is considered one of the problems that have not been well studied in the science of psychology. This problem was formed in the middle of the 20th century. The psychological approach is based on distinguishing the social-psychological difference of individual manifestations of deviant behavior. Psychological classifications are based on the following criteria:

- type of violated norm;
- morality and its psychological purpose in motivation;
- the consequences of this behavior and the damage it causes;
- a personal-methodical description of ethics.

It should be noted that the term "deviant behavior" can be applied to children under the age of 5, and strictly speaking, we can use it after the age of 9. Before the age of 5, the child does not have the necessary ideas about social norms, and self-control is carried out with the help of adults. Only at the age of 9-10, it is possible to talk about the ability of a child to independently observe social norms. If the behavior of children younger than 5 years deviates significantly from the age norm, then it is appropriate to consider it as a manifestation of immaturity, nervous reaction or mental development disorder.

Destructive behavior is manifested in 2 main types:

1. The delinquent type is the orientation of behavior to actions that are contrary to the social and legal norms accepted in society.
2. The deviant type is the manifestation of moral views contrary to the moral standards accepted in society.

In all forms of destructive behavior, it occurs as a certain protective reaction of a person, but it can be associated with disorders in the nervous system. Destructive behavior can be caused by negative emotional experiences in childhood, emotional coldness of parents towards the child, lack of love from them at the necessary time, and hereditary factors.

Z. Freud states that there are 2 main instincts in human behavior: Eros is the instinct of life. The power in it directs to preservation and restoration of life. Thanatos is the death instinct. Its power directs to destroy and stop life. Destructive behavior is common to all people. In some people, this behavior is so strong that it determines their position and behavior in society.

In the manifestation of destructive behavior, negative assumptions are formed as a result of negative attitudes of the person towards the majority of those around him. In S.P. Ivanov and V.V. Boyko's studies, the following types of destructive devices are distinguished:

1. Hidden carelessness in thoughts and actions towards others;
2. Open carelessness towards others;
3. Based on negative thoughts about people. It is the same with having a negative opinion about the people who caused it based on the circumstances that arose in certain social situations;

4. Making unfounded generalizations about one's partners due to negative factors;

5. Having a negative experience in the process of relationships with others
Kleiberg Yu. A and A. Ellis introduced the concept of "irrational assumptions" in the formation of destructive behaviors.

According to Lombroso, based on his conclusions about biological characteristics and, first of all, external morphological characteristics (the shape of the skull), the result of the innate characteristics of criminals, he considered crime inevitable and said that punishment could not correct them. Lombroso developed the most sought-after formula in the criminology of crime. In his formula, the founder of the Institute of Anthropology suggests connecting the average size of the anthropological characteristics of prisoners with the number of minors who consumed alcohol.

Interest in the development of genetics increased significantly, and the chromosomal hypothesis of aggression and crime was developed.

Another direction of biological theories of aggression is related to the study of the role of hormonal influences on criminal and aggressive behavior. In 1924, the American scientist M. Schlapp studied the endocrine system of criminals, he found that one-third of the prisoners he examined suffered from emotional instability.

We see that the various manifestations of deviant behavior of a person are located on the single axis of "destructive morality" with two opposite directions - to oneself or to others.

The first and most important institution of social control in human education is the family. A healthy family environment plays an important role in raising a child and forming a mature generation. A child lives in a family environment from the day of his birth. Family traditions, values, and customs form a child's personality. The most important thing is that children understand and feel the demands of society through the school of family life. The place and role of the direct officials and heads of organizations for educational processes is great for the formation of the personal views of the members of the society, for the composition of their socially active attitudes towards deviant behavior. "It's possible for some, it's not possible for others", "good now, bad tomorrow" and similar attitudes it is very dangerous to allow it to act in the form of a secondary character, that is, in the direction of parallel standards. Therefore, violation of the norms of behavior by officials, leaders of various public organizations and labor

unions, pedagogues and educators, and representatives of law enforcement organizations is strictly condemned in any case.

Each of the social evils related to alcoholism, drug addiction, and suicide, which are deviant behaviors, have essentially different aspects according to their occurrence and social consequences. The first difference is that the long-term continuation of socially harmful habits is that deviant behavior becomes an integral part of the lifestyle. Constant family disagreements, dissatisfaction with the family and environment, misunderstandings at home, etc. - all this hurts the psyche of the subject and he tries to change the existing situation.

In society, the activities, actions and behaviors of people are governed by social norms. Elimination of destructive behavior, social norms are an integral part of the management of society, and we must achieve compliance with the rules that adapt the behavior of an individual or a social group to a specific social environment.

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